

Effects of Psychosocial Hazards on Young Women Engaged in Grain Value Chain Activities in North Central, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the effects of psychosocial hazards on young women engaged in grain value chain in North Central, Nigeria. The study described the socio-economic characteristics of the women, described their involvement in grain value chain and assessed the effects of psychosocial hazards they were exposed to in grain value chain in the study area. Multi-staged sampling procedures were used in selecting one hundred and ninety-four (194) young women between 20-40 years. The instruments used were interview schedule, focus group discussion (FGD), key informant Interview (KII) and participant observation (PO). The statistical tools used were frequency count, percentage, mean score, standard deviation and Pearson correlation for inferential statistics. The respondents had a mean age of 30.57 ± 5.24 years, 8.43 ± 3.02 years of schooling, marketing experience was 15.51 ± 8.03 years and 156.01 ± 119.68 km distance of market from home; 63.40% were married, 100 percent travelled by road. The respondents' involvement in grain value chain reported high were travelling to market (4.49), purchasing and aggregating (4.26) and price negotiation (4.25). The effects of psychosocial hazards reported severe were armed robbery (4.32), mental stress (4.25), kidnapping (4.21), rape (4.11), anxiety (4.00) and killing (3.98) all have mean scores above or very close to the grand mean of 3.89. Involvement in activities in grain value chain and effects of psychosocial hazards had p-value of (0.01). The study found that the young women confronted limitless number of psychosocial hazards, which hampered their wellbeing. Therefore, the study recommended implementation of waybill systems and improved internet connectivity; enforcement of grain grading and standardization by the government agencies; government commitment to infrastructural development; provision of therapeutic procedures, education on sexual violence for young women and free treatment for rape victims.

Key words: Hazards, young women, vulnerability, grain value chain

INTRODUCTION

Globally, agriculture is a cornerstone of the world economy, employing 1.3 billion people, according to the International Labour Organization (2023). This sector is not just a source of food but also a significant employer, particularly for women. In sub-Saharan Africa, women make up 60-80% of the agricultural labour force, as noted by the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO, 2021). According to Amusan *et al.*, (2021), Nigeria's economy is heavily dependent on agriculture, which accounts for 70% of its workforce and approximately 25% of its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Within this sector, women are vital contributors, estimated to be responsible for 65% of the country's agricultural output, including food grains. Young women, in particular, play a critical role in ensuring food availability and accessibility through their work as itinerant travelers or bulk sellers, a primary source of their economic livelihood. Food grains including cereals, pulses and oilseeds are the nutritional bedrock of Nigeria, providing 46% of calories and 52% of proteins consumed, these crops are crucial for both human and animal consumption, as well as industrial use (Petrikova *et al.*, 2022).

Women are key players in the grain value chain, participating in every stage from providing inputs to

reaching the final consumer. As market women and informal agricultural traders, their work involves traveling between local and regional markets on specific days to buy and sell goods, (Adeola and Etiebet, 2019). This mobility, while essential for the economy, exposes them to significant challenges; for instance, the rising violence from terrorist groups, bandits and armed robbers poses a major threat, potentially leading to disruptions in the food supply, property loss and even fatalities (Onuoha, 2020). According to Etebu and Odiri, (2023) the collective nature of these gatherings of market women on market days highlights the shared risks they face. This precarious environment, combined with a lack of control and limited social support, creates significant gender-based psychosocial hazards. These stressors can negatively affect their productivity, performance, functionality and overall well-being.

Despite over three decades of utilizing agricultural value chain development for rural transformation and poverty alleviation, North Central, Nigeria faces ongoing challenges in achieving development outcomes that simultaneously ensure pro-poor value chains, empower women and vulnerable groups like itinerants and mitigate the psychosocial hazards that these young women experience in their daily work. Ihalainen, (2020) suggest that while value chains may

benefit women, they also exacerbate gender inequalities. Although occupational hazards are a well-researched area, which were findings by Amoako, (2019) in a research on maternal market traders in Accra, Ghana, highlights that unhealthy market conditions in or near slums significantly threaten the health and well-being of women; Habibi *et al.*, (2024) in their research titled “Climate Change and Occupational Heat Strain among Women Workers”: A Systematic Review, but psychosocial hazards confronting young women, particularly itinerants in the grain value chain remain under studied. Given the significant contribution of young women to Nigeria's grain value chain, especially itinerants; their well-being is crucial for national growth and development. The right to health, a fundamental human right, is a key objective of social and economic progress. The World Health Organization (WHO, 2002) asserts that the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is a fundamental right for all regardless of their circumstances. This right applies to women as all individuals are entitled to a work environment that minimizes health risks. Furthermore, UN Women, (1995) during the Beijing Declaration of 1995 highlights the holistic nature of women's health, encompassing their physical, social and emotional well-being and its dependence on the social, political and economic factors shaping their lives. For itinerant young women, these factors include the challenges of informal work and potential exposure to psychosocial hazards.

This study assessed the effects of psychosocial hazards on young women engaged in grain value chain (GVC) activities in the North Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the study objectives were to: describe the socio-economic characteristics of young women engaged in GVC activities and describe the involvement of young women engaged in grain value chain activities (Travelling to buy grains, Purchasing, Aggregating, Price negotiation, Transporting grains to destinations, Drying, Sorting etc.) in the study area. The hypothesis states that there is no significant relationship between involvement in grain value chain by the women actors and effects of psychosocial hazards on women in grain VC.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area and Sample

The research was conducted in North Central Nigeria, a region comprising six states (Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger and Plateau) and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. With a female population of approximately 9.8 million National Bureau of

Statistics (NBC, 2022), the area lies between latitudes 7°00' and 11°30' North and longitudes 4°00' and 11°00' East. The region has a tropical continental climate with distinct wet and dry seasons. The wet season is characterized by an average annual rainfall of 1,200mm to 1,500mm, is ideal for the rain-fed agriculture prevalent in the area. The dry season from November to February, is marked by the cold, hazy weather of the Harmattan winds. The diverse vegetation, which includes the Guinea, Sudan and Sahel savannah belts, supports a wide range of crops. This ecological diversity makes the region suitable for growing staples like cassava, yam and potatoes, as well as cereals, such as rice, millet, sorghum maize, acha, beniseed, groundnuts, soybeans, fruits and vegetables. (Olanrewaju and Fayemi, 2015).

The study's population consisted of all young women (20-40 years) involved in the grain value chain in the North Central region of Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select the respondents. The first stage involved the purposive selection of three States (Kogi, Kwara and Niger) from the six States in the region. The second stage involved the purposive selection of two Agricultural Development Programme (ADP) Zones from each of the three States, resulting in six (6) ADP zones. The third stage was the purposive selection of 25% of the sixty-three (63) markets in the Zones resulting in 16 markets. The breakdown of markets in these zones were as follows: Kogi Zone A had eight (8) markets and Zone C had twelve (12); Kwara Zone B had seven (7) markets and Zone D had thirteen (13); and Niger Zone I had twelve (12) markets and Zone II had eleven (11). The final stage of sampling involved a stratified random selection of 10% of the registered young women grain traders from each of the 16 markets. This yielded one hundred and ninety-four (194) respondents, with the number of women selected from each market varying based on its size. Twelve (12) women were chosen from Girinya, fifteen (15) from Lokoja, thirteen (13) from Kabba/Bunu, and ten (10) from Isanlu and nine (9) from Egbe. In Kwara, thirteen (13) were selected from Patigi, sixteen (16) from Gbugbu, twelve (12) from Offa, eight (8) from Oke-Ode, and ten (10) from Eruku. Niger, eleven (11) were chosen from Mokwa, twelve (12) from Bida, eleven (11) from Lapai, fifteen (15) from Lambata, thirteen (13) from Gwada, and fourteen (14) from Maikunkele. This process yielded one hundred and ninety-four (194) respondents. The number of women selected from each market varied based on the size of the market.

Primary data were collected through an interview schedule, focus group discussion (FGD), key informant interview (KII) and participant observation (PO). Descriptive statistics involving the use of frequency counts mean score, percentages and standard deviation while inferential statistics was drawn using Pearson Correlation. Independent variables were socio-economic characteristics; involvement of women in grain value chain was measured on 5-point Likert scale of Very Low=1, L=2, Moderate=3, High=4 and Very High=5. Grand mean was used to rank involvement as High, Moderate and Low. Effects of psychosocial hazards was the dependent variable which comprises psychosocial hazards in grain value chain and these were measured on a 5-point Likert type of Not Severe=1, Severe=2, Moderately Severe =3 and Severe=4 and Very Severe =5. In calculating the overall effects of psychosocial hazards on women actors in GVC, the grand mean was used. When the score is above the grand mean, the effects of the psychosocial hazard is very severe, when the score is hovers around the grand mean the effects of the psychosocial hazard is moderately severe and when the score is below the grand mean the effects of the psychosocial hazard is not severe.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results in Table 1 show that the mean age of respondents was 30.57 ± 5.24 years. About 46.90% of the respondents were less than or equal to 30 years while 53.09% fell between 31 to 40 years. This characteristic implies that these women possess the requisite physical vigour, energy and capacity to contribute substantially to the economic activities of their respective communities. This finding resonates with the research by Omotesho *et al.*, (2019) which highlighted the deep engagement of women, across various agricultural activities, from production to marketing in Kwara State, Nigeria. Furthermore, it corroborates the observations of Maereka *et al.* (2023) whose study, similarly reported the active participation of younger women in bean production and marketing. Table 1 also reveals that 63.40% of the respondents were married while 36.58% were single, by (7.73% unmarried, 20.61% were widowed, 5.67% were separated while 2.57% were divorced). The predominant marital status among these young women engaged in GVC in the study area implies that the majority were married. This status influences their level of engagement in the grain value chain, with married women possibly exhibiting a reduced intensity of involvement compared to their single counterparts. A potential consequence of this reduced involvement could be a diminished exposure to

psychosocial hazards inherent in the grain business. On the other hand, single women in this sector may experience an amplified burden of responsibilities, compelling them to exert additional effort in their work. This observation is consistent with the general understanding that married individuals tend to exhibit better health outcomes on average when compared to single, divorced, separated or widowed individuals. This finding corroborates Musa, (2019) who similarly reported that single women often face greater family responsibilities, necessitating more diligent work to secure their livelihoods due to a lack of spousal support.

Further results in Table 1 show the mean score and standard deviation (SD) of year(s) of schooling as 8.33 ± 2.89 . About 23.19% respondents had between 1 - 6 years of schooling and 56.70% had between 7 - 11 years. The findings suggest that the adoption and practical implementation of health related innovations among young women engaged in the grains value chain will be facilitated. This finding is affirmed by Malhora *et al.*, (2023) that formal education empowers women to engage in more effective negotiations with diverse value chain stakeholders, ranging from input suppliers to buyers, thereby securing more equitable terms of trade. Education also cultivates greater receptiveness to and adoption of modern agricultural technologies, better health and innovative practices, which, in turn, leads to increased efficiency and productivity. In addition, showing in the Table was the average household size of 5 ± 1.69 persons; this suggests a prevalent pattern of extended family structures or larger cohabiting units, implying a significant demand on household resources and consequently a necessity for substantial effort in providing for the family's sustenance.

Table 1 also shows the mean score of the respondents' years of marketing experience as 15.51 ± 8.03 years. Below one third, (29.89%) had between 1 and 10 years of experience, 38.66% had between 11 and 20 years of experience, while 31.44 had between 21-30 years in grains business experience. This finding suggests that the majority of the young women engaged in the grain value chain possess substantial experience, which can be through inheritance and this is likely to enhance their decision-making capabilities. This observation aligns with the findings of Saleh and Mustapha (2018) that there is a positive correlation between years of job experience and increased productivity in Nigeria. Therefore, the accumulated practical knowledge among these young women actors appears to be a significant asset, contributing to their effective participation and potential for improved outcomes

within the grain sector. Also on Table 1 was the annual income of the respondents, which was on the average of ₦ 2,435,784.54±971138.19. Also revealed on Table 1 was the average distance travelled by the young women which was 156.01±119.68 Km. This finding indicates a high degree of cosmopolitans among the women actors, suggesting they were not confined to their immediate localities. Their extensive travel, both near and far, for grain procurement highlights the critical role of long-distance trade in their livelihoods. This observation aligns with historical accounts from Raji and Abejide (2013) which highlight the economic importance of long-distance trade to Yorubaland's economy during the

19th century, despite prevalent insecurity at the time. The whole 100% of the respondents travelled by road, 6.09% travelled by water while 5.80% travelled by rail. The findings indicate that respondents utilized various available transportation modes, with road transport being the primary and most consistently accessible option across different regions despite the deplorable states of the road, which predisposed them to various psychosocial hazards. This observation aligns with the realities of Nigeria's transportation infrastructure. This corroborates the findings of Adeseyi (2013) that railway transportation in Nigeria has been experiencing crisis in the last three decades.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of respondents by Age, Marital Status, Years of Schooling and Household Size

Variables	Freq. (194)	Percentage (%)	Mean Score(±SD)
Age (years)			
<=30	91	46.90	30.57±5.24
31-40	103	53.09	
Marital Status			
Single	15	7.73	
Married	123	63.40	
Widowed	40	20.61	
Separated	11	5.67	
Divorced	5	2.57	
Year(s) of Schooling			
1 – 6	45	23.19	8.43±3.02
7-11	110	56.70	
=>12	39	20.10	
Householdsize (persons)			
<=2	5	2.57	5±1.69
3 – 4	62	31.95	
5 – 6	70	36.08	
7 – 8	57	29.38	
Year(s) of Marketing Experience			
<=10	58	29.89	15.51±8.03
11-20	75	38.66	
21-30	61	31.44	
Annual Income (Naira)			
1000001 – 2000000	77	39.69	2,435,784.54± 971138.19
2000001 – 3000000	73	37.62	
3000001 – 4000000	23	11.85	
4000001 >	21	10.82	
Distance of Market from Home(Km)			
<=100	64	32.98	156.01±119.68
101-200	81	41.75	
201-300	17	8.76	
301-400	18	9.27	
>400	14	7.21	
Means of Transportation***			
Road	194	100	

Water	21	6.09
Rail	20	5.8

Source: Field Survey, 2024 *** Multiple responses

Involvement of Young Women Engaged in Grain Value Chain

Table 2 reveals the mean scores well above the grand mean of 3.18 are concentrated at the initial stages of the value chain. These include travelling to markets to buy grains (4.49), purchasing of grains (4.26), aggregating of grains (4.26) and negotiating for price (4.25). In contrast, activities with the lowest involvement, with mean scores significantly below the grand mean, are primarily related to production and logistics. These include production of grains (1.74), contract farming (1.76), input supply to farmers (1.79) and packaging of grains (2.09). This clear disparity indicates that young women are highly involved in the trading and aggregation of grains but have minimal participation in the foundational production and physical labour aspects of the value chain.

Given the inherently heavy, bulky and labourious nature of these activities, women's extensive engagement, even at varying degrees, suggests a substantial exposure to psychosocial hazards at virtually every node of the value chain as they strive for livelihood. This observation aligns with the research of Nicholas and McDonald, (2010) that highlighted the dual burden faced by women in developing nations, often involving both household responsibilities and demanding manual labour in occupations that frequently exceed their physical capacities. The present study further underscores the disproportionate physical and mental demands placed upon women within the agricultural sector, necessitating a closer examination of the resultant psychosocial impacts.

Table 2: Involvement of Women Actors in Grain Value Chain

Variables	VL %	L %	M %	H %	VH %	Cumm. Score	Mean Score	Rank
Travelling to markets to buy grains	00	00	00	50.1	49.9	1552	4.49	1 st
Purchasing of grains	00	00	00	73.3	26.7	1472	4.27	2 nd
Aggregating of grains	00	00	00	73.6	26.4	1471	4.26	3 rd
Negotiating for price	00	00	00	74.2	25.8	1469	4.25	4 th
Transporting of grains to my destinations	00	00	00	97.7	2.3	1388	4.02	5 th
Drying of grains	00	00	00	100	00	1380	4.0	6 th
Storing of grains in store	00	00	00	100	00	1380	4.0	6 th
Grading of grains	00	00	00	100	00	1380	4.0	6 th
Advertising of grains	00	00	25.5	74.5	00	1292	3.75	9 th
Processing of grains	00	00	25.8	74.2	00	1291	3.74	10 th
Labeling of bags	00	00	68.7	29.0	2.3	1151	3.33	11 th
Fumigating of grains in store	00	22.6	23.2	53.6	0.6	1146	3.32	12 th
Bagging of grains	00	47.5	00	26.1	26.4	1143	3.31	13 th
Classifying grain types	25.2	00	23.8	50.7	0.3	1125	3.26	14 th
Distribution of grains to retailers	00	25.5	24.1	50.4	00	1121	3.24	15 th
Sorting of grains	24.1	00	47.8	27.0	1.2	970	2.81	16 th
Off-loading of grains bags	00	72.2	00	27.5	0.3	883	2.55	17 th
Stacking of grains bags	00	74.2	00	25.8	00	868	2.51	18 th
Harvesting of grains	25.8	00	74.2	00	00	857	2.48	19 th
Loading of grains bags into vehicles	00	73.0	25.8	0.6	0.6	789	2.28	20 th
Grains sack sewing	00	73.3	25.8	0.9	00	785	2.27	21 st
Packaging of grains	47.0	24.6	00	28.4	00	724	2.09	23 rd
Input supply to farmers	73.6	00	00	26.1	0.3	619	1.79	23 rd
Contract Farming	49.6	24.6	25.8	00	00	608	1.76	24 th
Production of grains	25.8	74.2	00	00	00	601	1.74	25 th

Source: Field Survey, 2024

VL= Very Low, L= Low, M=Moderate, H= High, VH= Very High

Effects of Psychosocial Hazards

Table 3 shows the grand mean was 3.89 and the effects are as ranked, armed robbery (4.32= 1st), mental stress (4.25=2nd), kidnapping (4.21=3rd), rape (4.11=4th), anxiety (4.00=5th) and killing (3.98=6th). This implies that these hazards are the most significant threats to the women in this sector. The findings implies that severe psychosocial pose a direct and significant threat to the young women's ability to sustain their livelihood. These extreme risks can lead to physical harm, psychological trauma and a loss of personal and financial resources, ultimately disrupting their work and economic stability. These results corroborate Msheila *et al.*, (2024) that identified insecurity as a primary impediment negatively affecting women's entrepreneurial endeavors in Shiroro LGA, as reported by an overwhelming majority of their respondents.

This also aligns with the descriptions of occupational burn out provided by Shanafelt and Swensen, (2017) whose characterizations include the development of a cynical attitude towards work, severe lack of motivation, erratic sleeping patterns and profound disillusionment concerning one's occupation. Evidence of these threats is underscored by recent media accounts, such as the report by Akote, (2024) documented the invasion, killings and abduction of market women in Madaka, Rafi LGA, Niger State. Similarly, Mumin, (2024) reported the ambush and abduction of eleven market women going to Oke-Ode Market in Ifelodun LGA, Kwara State.

Responses from discussants:

Mrs. A from Lapai reports that rapes happens quite often, but it is not easy to disclose due to police bureaucracy and societal stigmatization.

Mrs. M from Patigi reports: I have reduced travelling drastically since an encounter with kidnappers where I was able to escape, but some of the commuters could not make it home that day until ransom was paid”.

Response from a key informant at Gbugbu Market:

I have seen grains business as my life and I am living it despite the challenges I face.

Participant Observation (PO):

It was observed during the course of this study that bad roads contribute majorly to insecurity of the women itinerants in grain value chain.

It can also be deduced here that the pervasive insecurity and inherent risks faced by women in the grain value chain therefore not only impede their economic activities but also pose substantial threats to their mental and physical well-being. Women actors in grains value chain's life are endangered through their means of livelihood.

Table 3: Effects of Psychosocial Hazards

Risks	NS %	SS %	MS %	S %	VS %	Cumm. Score	Mean Score	Rank
Psychosocial Hazards								
Armed robbery	00	3.5	5.5	46.1	44.9	1492	4.32	1 st
Mental Stress	0.6	8.1	5.5	36.8	49.0	1468	4.25	2 nd
Kidnapping	00	1.2	23.5	28.4	47.0	1453	4.21	3 rd
Rape	00	1.7	18.0	47.0	33.3	1421	4.11	4 th
Killing	00	5.5	17.1	49.0	28.4	1381	4.00	5 th
Discrimination	00	00	31.6	38.0	30.4	1376	3.98	6 th
Pick pocketing	00	18.3	16.5	39.1	26.1	1287	3.73	7 th
Harassment	1.7	5.5	36.8	45.5	10.4	1233	3.57	8 th
Fights	13.9	31.9	19.7	26.4	8.1	976	2.82	9 th

Source: Field Survey, 2024

NS= Not severe, SS=Slightly Severe, MS= Moderately Severe, S=Severe, VS= Very Severe

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between involvement by young women engaged in grain value chain and effects of psychosocial hazards on young women engaged in GVC.

Table 4 presents the correlation between the involvement by young women engaged in grain value chain and effects of psychosocial hazards on young women engaged in GVC. The analysis reveals a statistically significant relationship between the involvement by women actors in the grain value chain and their exposure to psychosocial hazards. This relationship is significant at the 1% level of probability ($p < 0.01$), indicating a strong positive

correlation. Specifically, the findings demonstrate that a higher involvement in grain value chain is associated with a greater exposure to psychosocial hazards.

Based on this statistically significant result, the null hypothesis, which posited that there is no significant relationship between involvement by young women in grain value chain and effects of psychosocial hazards on young women engaged in grains value chain, is therefore rejected. This rejection underscores the direct and substantial link between the extent of young women's involvement in these activities and their vulnerability to psychosocial risks.

Table 4: Correlation between the Involvement of Young Women Engaged in Grain Value Chain Activities and the Effects of Psychosocial Hazards on the Young Women Engaged in Grains VC.

Variables	P value	Coef.	Decision
Involvement in Grains Value Chain	0.000	0.874**	S

Source: Field Survey, 2024 **Significance

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that young women engaged in the grain business in the study area were married, fell within their active age, had average level of formal education and had considerable size of household. The women possessed substantial experience of marketing experience and travelled wide to source for grains. Their deep involvement in the GVC for ensuring accessibility and availability of grains to the populace is fraught with varying degrees of

psychosocial hazards. Based on the findings, these recommendations were made: implementation of waybill system and improved internet service by service providers; enforcement of grain standardization by the government agencies, improved infrastructural services and security by the government; and free therapeutic procedures for rape victims by the government and Non-Government Organizations.

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